

The Civil Service and Service Delivery in Rivers State (Nigeria) in 2015-2023: A Comparative Perspective

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Abstract

This study examined the role of the civil service in public policy implementation in Rivers State, Nigeria, from 2007 - 2023. The Ministries selected were: Ministry of Education, Ministry of Health and Ministry of Agriculture. The theoretical framework adopted was the Bureaucratic Politics Model as propagated by Graham T. Allison between the 1950's and the 1960's. Data were obtained from both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources were from oral interviews of some serving and retired Permanent Secretaries and Directors/Heads of Department in the selected Ministries, while secondary data were obtained from publications, annual reports, news magazines and bulletins, as well as brochures from selected Ministries. Interviews were carried out with a total of thirty (30) retired and serving officials. Findings from this study showed that the Rivers State Civil Service operated in line with the stipulated regulations guiding it, but there were some sort of discrepancies between the two administrations under study on the use of civil servants in policy formulation and implementation, hence the observed inconsistency in policies of successive administrations. Based on the findings, this study recommended amongst others that Permanent Secretaries should be statutory members of the Rivers State Executive Council; the Rivers State Government should establish an administrative Training Institute to train and re-train senior civil servants in the State.

Keywords: *Civil Service, Service Delivery, Policy Implementation, Rivers State.*

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Introduction

There is no gainsaying that the responsibility of the State in any social formation is the security of lives and property, as well as provision for the welfare of the citizenry. These responsibilities are achieved by the State through government machinery. Governments achieve their objectives through programmes and policies and the civil service of the State is the implementation organ of such policies and programmes. The increasing rate of government activities has seen the function and scope of government broaden. Modern government has assumed enormous responsibilities, in education, health, agriculture, social welfare, infrastructure development, amongst others, thus the importance of policy measures and implementation instruments. This ever increasing scope of government activities has necessitated the need for a more viable and efficient civil service and as such the need to interrogate the activities of the service and its role in the overall development of the State, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria.

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Since the emergence of the Fourth Republic in Nigeria, successive governments have made frantic efforts to meet their constitutional responsibilities of protecting lives and property of the citizenry, as well as providing for their welfare. The services provided by government are carried out through public service initiatives, while the civil service is the body of officials that gives effect to such policies by way of implementation. This assertion is supported by Adebayo (1986, p. 85) when he opined that “The main functions of the civil service may be summarised as follows: to implement and execute the policies and decisions of those in authority who decide policy”. There is no doubt that the Nigerian civil service is one of the significant legacies left by the colonialists, which serves as a functional tool required to put the nation on the path of recovery that could match the rising expectations of the people savouring the euphoria of independence (Adedire, 2014; 2016) and so cannot be glossed over. Consequent upon this realisation, we can argue that the civil service as the name implies is oriented towards service to the State and the success or failure of the service is dependent on policy outcome and so their roles in policy formulation and implementation become relevant. It is in this regard that this paper examines the role the civil service played in the attainment of the overall objectives of government during the period under review.

Literature Review

The concept of civil service and its literature appears simplistic, concise and straight forward. However, like the numerous concepts in the social sciences, various scholars and practitioners have bared their minds on the concept based on their ideological leanings and practical experiences. However, the misplacement the concept has attracted, particularly in its usage by scholars and practitioners alike brings to bare the need for defined clarifications as most often the concept civil service is used interchangeable with the term public service. In this regard, Epelle (2007) expresses his view to the lack of unanimity in the operationalisation of the concept civil service. This, apparently, is the reason why the two terms have been used interchangeable and thus makes it imperative to explain the two terms as far as this study is concerned. According to Arowolo (2012), the public service is a body or department in the executive arm of government with the responsibility of assisting in the planning and implementation of government policies. It is not profit-oriented but an institution established to deliver essential services to the people (Shimawu, 2020). The public service includes the following: The Civil Service- the career personnel of the Presidency, Ministers, Extra- ministerial Departments, the National Assembly and the Judiciary; the Armed Forces, the Police, other Security agencies, e.g. para-military organisations, as well as parastatals or public enterprises (Marshall & Murtala, 2015).

Section 169 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria defines the public service as encompassing the civil service (ministerial departments), statutory corporation or parastatals, judiciary, legislature, educational institutions, financially wholly or partially owned by government at the State, Local and Federal levels, Nigeria Police or Armed Forces and other organisations in which the Federal or State governments own controlling share of interests (Fagbemi, 2020). Shittu (2020), on his part, opines that the public service in any country of the world represents the machinery of government through which public policies are formulated and implemented and that public service achieves this function by converting government policies and programmes into tangible goods and services for consumption of the citizenry (Shittu, 2020). Examining Nigerian public service performance in a dysfunctional ecology, Osawe (2015) avers that the public service reflects the state of the nation and no nation has been able to advance beyond its public service as studies have shown that no nation can attain sustainable development for the enhancement of the living standard of the people without a properly organised public service to implement government policies (Akindele, Okanlawon, & Olusesi, 2023).

Marshall and Murtala (2015) are of the view that the civil service is an organ created to ensure that policies and programmes of any government at any particular time are carried out. To this end, the civil service as part of government never dies because of its perpetual nature and the changing nature of constitutionally elected government; it has to be endowed with specific qualities or leanings of that government.

On its part, the Federal Government of Nigeria (1997) defines the civil service as “a body or organ which enjoys continuity of existence. Its members unlike the members of the National Assembly are not limited to a short term office at the end of which they may not be returned to office. When a civil servant relinquishes his office for whatever reason, his place is taken by another person who similarly enjoys security of employment (Osawe, 2015). Civil service consists of civil servants and their activity when implementing the assigned functions and decisions made by politicians. In other words, it is a system of civil servants who perform the assigned functions of public administration (Smalskys & Urbanovic, 2017). Omoruyi (1991), in his contribution, identifies civil service as a wide organisation that is controlled and funded by the government. It involves bureaucrats and technocrats of the state, not of political or judicial office holders employee in civil capacity with their remunerations paid wholly from money voted in the parliament (Nebo, & Nnamani, 2015). On his part, Anazodo (2006), opines that the civil service in Nigeria comprises of workers in various ministries, departments and agencies apart from political office holders (Nebo, & Nnamani, 2015). On his part, Bade (2009), defines the Nigerian civil service as a body of government employees entrusted with the administration of the country and mandated to carry out the policies of the government of the day. In other words, it is a body of civilian employees of any level of government, not subject to political appointment and removal, normally hired and promoted largely on the basis of competitive examination.

Characteristics of the Civil Service

The civil service has a number of characteristics which a number of scholars have enumerated. Onah (2013) outlining the features of the civil service identifies the following: Comprehensiveness; permanence; political neutrality anonymity, as well as good conduct and discipline. She refers to them as norms and ethics of the civil service. According to her, the civil service is comprehensive because the services and responsibilities cover and affects all aspects of lives of the citizens of the country and that government of any modern state has powers to make policies, rules and regulations governing every aspect of life of a state. Epelle (2020) also identifies: permanence, impartiality, expertise, anonymity, as well as meritocracy as characteristics of the civil service. As regards expertise, he states that a civil servant is supposed to be an administrator par excellence in the discharge of his duties and always ready to take on challenges as they occur and that the reason is because political executives who serve as chief executives or ministers of government are most times professionals in areas outside of administration, it will therefore be unfair to have expected them to be totally conversant with the operations of government and implications of public policies and programmes. For Obiajulu & Obi (2008), the civil service is guided by the triple maxims of anonymity, neutrality and impartiality in addition to the principle of permanence.

Marshall and Murttala (2015) on their part outline the characteristics of the civil service thus: It has to be non-partisan to enable it serve any government of the day; it has to be made up of experienced men and women with the technical and professional knowledge to enable them implement government policies; it has to be orderly and also ensure that orderly administration of the country continues is indispensable since it continues the traditional role of keeping the functions of government running, no matter what changes occur in the country, and that it operates under rules which guide its conduct (Fagbemi, et al., 2013). It is evident that the characteristics of the civil service form the core principles on which the activities of the civil service revolve.

Importance of the Civil Service

The aforementioned views of the characteristics of the civil service is indicative of the important role it plays in the machinery of administration to achieve the objectives of the government of the day. As regards the importance of the civil service in the State, Onah (2013) avers that since it is the civil service machinery that is mainly responsible for the execution and implementation of government policies and programmes, it follows that the effectiveness of any government depends largely on the civil service

(Nwanegbo, 2015). To this end, she argues that the civil service is the main instrument which mirrors the image of the government to the masses.

Underscoring the importance of the civil service in the overall development of the State, the Federal Government of Nigeria, (2011) avers that a committed civil service is the vehicle for carrying out and explaining to the people, the policies and intentions of government and that there is no better and ready instrument available to a government to influence the moral tone of the nation than a well-motivated and appreciated civil service that is thereby enabled to perform its duty of service to its master, the government and to the people amongst whom the bulk of those who man the civil service live.

For Epelle (2020), the primary role of the civil service is to implement government policies, programmes and projects. According to him, in modern societies, where the three organs of government are carrying out their respective functions as prescribed by law after the legislature of the State has made the law and the judiciary has interpreted knotty aspects of the law, it is now left for the executive to carry out the law as promulgated by the other two arms. Furthermore, he avers that the civil service is an indispensable repository of knowledge from which the political executives draw as they mount the saddle of leadership of the State. For him, in new States and even the old ones, the civil service makes it possible for the neophyte executives to have a kind of knowledge bank to fall back on as the need arises and that it is puerile to imagine that as politicians pass the mantle of leadership to their successors, the latter will have all the facts of the workings of government, all ideas of subsisting policies and programmes and all data on government contracts and obligations in a handover note.

Obiajulu and Obi (2008), on their part, aver that the function of the civil service is the implementation of government policies, as civil servants are not policy makers and are not really in a position to question government policies (Kalu, & Ogali, 2021). Whenever a policy is made, it becomes the role of the civil servant to implement the policy the way the government of the day says it should be implemented (Kalu, & Ogali, 2021). On its part, the Federal Government of Nigeria (2010) states that essentially, the functions of the civil service are to:

- Contribute to translating the dreams and visions of the political/ruling class into concrete reality through the formulation of far-sighted policies and programmes and executing same loyally, conscientiously and effectively.
- Provide continuity between administrations.
- Serve as a unifying factor by bringing together people from all parts of the Federation and providing effective and adequate social services.
- Advise government on the full implications of various policy options open to it.
- Protect public interest as custodians of public conscience.
- Manage government data and information system effectively and efficiently so as to facilitate availability of data for government decision making.
- Operate an open, humane and sensitive system that ensures high professionalism, significant specialization, excellent motivation and high morale; and
- Ensure prompt effective and satisfying service delivery (Williams, 2010).

Contributing to the discourse Godwins (2019), citing Nwabueze states that the functions of the civil service may be circumscribed within the following seven points:

- the initiation of policy and advising government on the policy option open to it;
- execution of policy after it has been decided by government;
- administration of the laws enacted by the legislature;

- to provide continuity and to serve as a store of knowledge of past government decisions, policies and procedures;
- to serve as a factor of unity and stability in the polity;
- to serve as an embodiment of government in the day-to-day life of the people, and help preserve the mystique and authority of the government the daily contact of officials at all levels with the general public; and
- as part of the elite, to play the leadership role both within the service and in the community as a whole (Godwins, 2019).

Enumerating the role of the civil service in national development, Abah and Nwokwu (2017) opine that the role of the civil service in laying a solid foundation for national development cannot be over emphasised and that the service constitutes an engine of growth of any economy and hence national development is not contestable. To them, the Nigerian civil service has contributed to national development beginning from the earliest period of the British colonial rule in Nigeria. According to them, at that period, the earliest indigenous civil servants served colonial officials in the capacities of guards, messengers and interpreters and they provided support services to British colonial officials who manned the top echelon of the service.

Owoteme and Daniel (2021), writing on management of the civil service from the Nigerian perspective, highlight a number of causes of inefficiency in Nigeria's civil service (Owotemu, & Daniel, 2021). According to them, the Nigerian civil service has always performed poorly in terms of delivery on its mandate, thus several reforms have been initiated by previous administrations with a view to identifying and addressing the various challenges resulting in the poor performance of the sector and that in spite of the efforts, the civil service in Nigeria still remains largely inefficient and ineffective (Owotemu, & Daniel, 2021). They, however, identify: poor selection, orientation and training; tribalism, favouritism and nepotism; bureaucracy; bribery and corruption; political interference; over staffing and poor job description; as well as ineffective organisation as major problems faced by the civil service. Expanding on these factors, they argue that the process of recruiting new staff is usually flawed as there is no strategy put in place to select people who are competent and qualified for the position and that this process is usually non transparent and marred by a lot of irregularities, as well as the reality that those recruited are not properly oriented to their job requirements and trained to carry out their duties effectively (Owotemu, & Daniel, 2021). On the factor of tribalism, favouritism and nepotism, they assert that this is usually the reason for lack of transparency in the recruitment process and that it also affects promotions and postings which are usually not based on merit, but rather on tribal, religious or other mundane considerations, not related to job performance or suitability and that this invariably leads to putting square pegs in round holes, thus leading to poor performance on the job (Owotemu, & Daniel, 2021).

Nwanolue and Iwuoha (2012) in their study of the Nigerian civil service and promotion of sustainable human development are of the view that the civil service of any country is a moving force that pilots its administrative machinery. However, the fifty one years of existence of the Nigerian civil service *vis a vis* the promotion of sustainable human development and concluded that the civil service is still characterised by unequivocal sense of contradictory systematic malfunctions and profound character of administrative ineptitude, bureaucratic inertia and personality decay (Nwanolue, & Iwuoha, 2012). Nebo and Nnamaani (2015) interrogating the various civil service reforms and national development plans identify a number of challenges facing the civil service and their impact on national development in Nigeria. To them, the civil service in Nigeria is faced with myriads of problems and that this has made it difficult for the system to function effectively as a vehicle for national development (Nebo, & Nnamaani, 2015). They, on their part, also identify: politicisation; high level of corruption; fraught and discontent; poor remuneration; over bloated civil service; inadequate training and retraining, as well as the use of obsolete equipment as major challenges facing the civil service. With respect to fraught and discontent, they argue that lack of measurable objectives, inadequate evaluation, mismanagement of time, inadequate facilities, disorganisation, personnel management and over centralisation are internal weaknesses that have led

many public organisations to define their output, as money disbursed, rather than service delivered produce many low return, observable outputs, glossy reports and frameworks and few high return, less observable activities like ex-post evaluation, engage in obfuscation, spin control and official amnesia exhibiting little training from the past and putting enormous demands on administrative and technical skills (Nebo, & Nnamani, 2015).

With regards the challenges of poor remuneration, they argue that despite increment in salary, the civil service salary in Nigeria is still very low and that because of the poor salary remuneration, most civil servants engage in sharp practices as most of them keep business letter headed papers, invoices and receipts of various companies owned by them and because suppliers and contractors (Nebo, & Nnamani, 2015). This affects their contributions to service delivery and ultimately development of the state. They are also of the opinion that inadequate training and re training of civil servants affect productivity and service delivery and that even when training is undertaken, it is politicised and finally they assert that most government ministries, departments and agencies at federal, state and local levels still carry out their activities with obsolete equipment, such as manual typewriting machines in this age driven with high technology and to compound the situation, most civil servants are not Information Technology (IT) compliant and so hampers productivity and poses restraint to service delivery.

On his part Nwokoye (2012) identifies the issues of patronage, perceived corruption; operation inefficiency and poor service delivery; red tapism, recruitment process, as well as frequent changes in government as problems and challenges of the civil service. According to him, patronage is clearly a problem because it suggests the transgression of real or perceived boundaries of legitimate political influence, the violation of principles of merit and competition in the civil service recruitment and promotion (Tshombe, 2025). As regards operation inefficiency and poor service delivery, he is of the opinion that in terms of performance, it is often asserted that efficiency is low in the public sector and that the quality of service is poor and that operational inefficiency of the civil service comes about as a result of ineffective organisation, which usually leads to poor service delivery and that one possible outcome of this challenge is laxity amongst the workers and in most cases the exercise of discipline of workers is difficult. On the problem of red tapism, he argues that there is usually a rigid application of rules irrespective of the fact that such rules may no longer be in vogue and that when this happens; it either retards or kills personal initiatives and slows down the pace of work in the civil service, which in turn affects their efficiency. For him, too much bureaucracy usually affects the effectiveness and capacity of the civil service.

There is no doubt that the reoccurring vice of corruption as a major problem in Nigerian civil service makes it prominent as a major challenge to the service, as noted by scholars. To this end, Orluwene (2007) is of the opinion that a major problem confronting organisations in Nigeria is the effect or impact of corruption and that many studies have been conducted that show the evils and consequences of corruption. According to him, through corruption many political office holders acquire wealth and property in and outside Nigeria and much display their wealth, but the society does not blink. He goes further to outline the effects of corruption in Nigerian organisations as follows:

- It cripples government investment.
- It creates unemployment and attendant restiveness.
- It creates general poverty.
- It causes lack of development.

In his study of the Nigerian public service performance in a dysfunctional ecology, Osawo (2015) observes that given the number of policies that have been formulated in Nigeria since independence, public institutions of development, the human and natural resources the country is blessed with, the nation is supposed to have witnessed tremendous levels of social, economic and political development (Osawo, 2015). The reverse has, however, been the case and this underscores the fact that there has not been effective performance of the public service in the implementation of policies in Nigeria (Osawo,

2015). This reality, Ibietan and Joshua (2015) re-echo when they argue that the Nigerian bureaucracy lacks innovation in its mode of operation and that this is evidenced in the fact that most Nigerian civil servants have no modicum of knowledge regarding the goals of the service industry or those of governments in which they serve. While examining public sector performance in Nigeria, Ehiane, Adejuwon and Goyani (2019) observe that the failure of Nigeria to attain an appreciable level of development is attributed to the failure of the public service and suggest a reform of the public service in order to enhance control over administrative apparatus and to guarantee that it would become increasingly meritocratic and insulated from social interest. Also, in their study of the perception of young and middle aged adults about the public service in Nigeria, Oyekola, Ajani Asamu and Olajire (2021) discover that there was negative perception of Nigerian public service by the respondents and that this negative perception was higher in terms of its operation than in terms of its reward and as a result there was need for the improvement in operation of the operations and services of the public service to help in correcting this negative perception.

Theoretical Framework

This research work is hinged on the Bureaucratic Politics Model as propagated by Graham T. Allison between the 1950s and 1960s. Graham Allison is described as one of the foremost proponents of this model in his book *Essence of Decision: Explanation of the Cuban Crisis* published in 1971. The book applied within the bureaucracy often involved the Bureaucratic Politics Model to analyze the decision making process during the Cuban missile crisis of 1962 and since then the Model has been refined and expanded by numerous scholars (Allison & Halperin, 1972).

The Bureaucratic Politics Model is a theoretical framework used to analyze and understand decision making processes within government organizations and institutions. It suggests that civil servants are not merely passive implementers of public policies but are active players with their own interests, values and preferences. The theory also acknowledges that bureaucrats have specialized knowledge and expertise in their respective fields and can influence policy outcomes through their interactions with politicians, interest groups as well as other stakeholders. The theory also highlights the role of bureaucratic autonomy and discretion in policy implementation, It also focuses on the internal dynamics within the bureaucracy and highlighted the role of the civil servants in the policy making process.

According to this model, government agencies and departments consists of numerous individuals each with their own perspective on, expertise and organizational positions. These individuals are motivated to protect and advance their own interests and interest of their respective organizations. As a result, decision making is not solely based on rational analysis of policy options, but also shaped by the political dynamics within the bureaucracy

The Bureaucratic Model highlights three key components:

- i. **Bureaucratic Actors:** The Model emphasizes the role of key actors within the bureaucracy. These actors can include high level officials, policy makers, analysts and staff members. Each actor brings their own perspectives, biases and organizational interests to the decision making process
- ii. **Interests and Preferences:** Bureaucratic actors have different interests and preferences which can be influenced by their organizational goals, personal career aspirations or ideological beliefs. These interests and preferences shape the positions they take during policy debates and influence their strategies for achieving their desired outcomes.
- iii. **Bargaining and Negotiation:** Decision making within the bureaucracy often involves bargaining and negotiation among the various actors. They engage in strategic interactions, trying to secure the best outcome for their interests and preferences. This can involve forming alliances using information strategically, and employing various tactics to influence the decision making process (Clifford, 1990).

In relation to this study, the civil servant plays a crucial role in the policy formulation and implementation of the state, In Nigeria, the civil service has traditionally been seen as a very powerful institution with a significant influence on public policy. By applying the Bureaucratic politics Model, we can analyze how

civil servants shape policy decisions based on their expertise and experience on the job, bureaucratic interests and interactions with political elites. This theory helps to explain the internal negotiations, power struggles and policy compromises that occur within the civil service and between the civil servants and policy actors.

Again in Nigeria where the implementation gap is a significant challenge, understanding the bureaucratic dynamics can shed light on the factors that hinder or facilitate the effective formulation and implementation of public policies by civil servants. Applying this model in the Nigerian context provides insight on how civil servants influence policy formulation, negotiate competing interest, as well as navigate the complexities of the policy formulation process. It also helps to understand the motivations and strengths faced by civil servants in the relationship between the bureaucrats and politicians as well as the overall dynamics of public policy in Nigeria.

The Role of the Civil Service in Formulating Policies of the Rivers State Government from 2007-2021

A basic function of the civil servant is to help in providing assistance to government in policy formulation in the various sectors and divisions of society. This is against the reality that the civil servants are the field officers who interface between government and the people and so stand at a vintage position to provide useful information and expert knowledge that would enable political office holders take appropriate decisions on relevant public issues. To achieve this, the Guides to the Administrative Procedures in the Federal Civil Service, which is also domesticated at the State level, provides that it is the duty of the Permanent Secretary to provide the Commissioner with such useful information which the Commissioner is expected to take along and present before the State Executive Council. The Permanent Secretary is assisted by line officers (Directors/Heads of the various Departments in the Ministry). The Directors are the respective field officers who are in the field interfacing and implementing government policies and subsequently bring back feedback on policy outcomes by way of reporting back to the various Ministries.

Questions were posed to respondents to obtain information about the roles they play in their respective Ministries as regards the policy formulation in the respective sectors. The information gathered from the respondents in the Ministry of Education indicated that the Directors, who are experts in various fields of education, were consulted in areas of policy that concerned them. They met with their line officers which include: Deputy Directors, Assistant Directors, Administrative Officers, Administrative Assistants, who provided useful and relevant information that guided recommendations from the Department. Such recommendations were forwarded to the Permanent Secretary through a memo, which is, in turn, deliberated upon by the Management Team of the Ministry, before it is transmitted to the Executive Council through the Honourable Commissioner. In addition, the Directors carried out monitoring policy and compliance by public and private schools in Rivers State on the use of approved National Curriculum; approved list of books, approved academic calendar, etc, as well as conduct of annual school census for primary and secondary schools throughout the State. These were to maintain the quality in the standards provided in the sector in Rivers State. Also, four (4) respondents assert that their duties include supporting and contributing to the formulation and implementation of policies and programmes in Basic and Teacher Education Department and the Ministry at large.

As regards the policies formulated in the Rivers State Ministry of Education from 2007-2023, there (3) respondents in the Ministry of Education stated that they were involved in the introduction of model school policy by the government, policy on quality assurance, as well as policy guidelines on the operation of private schools. According to them, they provided useful information and data that enabled the government take appropriate decisions in this regard and also the stages of implementation and where to site the schools for the overall benefit of the citizens. This assertion was also confirmed in an oral interview with a retired Permanent Secretary who served in the Ministry of Education between 2007 and 2015 on August 27, 2024. According to him, “as Permanent Secretary, I was saddled with the

responsibility of helping shape policies of government by providing useful information and advice to the Honourable Commissioner who was the political Head of the Ministry. This was necessary because they were frequently changed and when such changes occur, it was my responsibility to put before the Commissioner, the policy direction of government on relevant issues pertaining the Ministry and that it was with such information that the Commissioner would be able to function”.

Two (2) Directors in the Ministry of Agriculture stated that their duties included providing agriculture information and library services and agro meteorology statistics. Monitoring and evaluation of the Ministry’s projects/ Programmes, play advisory role to the Honourable Commissioner on various agricultural policies, cover annual events such as World Food Day, as well as staff discipline; carry out policies , directives and instructions in line with the directives of the administrative structure of the Ministry. They further indicated that from 2007 -2015, the agricultural policies that were initiated included the Oil Palm Development Policy; Agro Industrial villages; Banana Plantation Development; Fish Farms Development Project; Rice Production Processing; Rubber Plantation; Rivers State Agricultural Development Programme (RSADP), Community Based Natural Resources Management Programme, FADAMA Programme, School–to-Land Programme, as well as the Songhai Farm Initiative. Under the period 2015-2023, the Ministry was able to facilitate the revisiting of the Revenue Law, as well as the decision that revenue head should be created for meat inspection and cattle and produce tax was also amended at the instance of the Honourable Commissioner for Agriculture.

A retired Permanent Secretary in the Ministry of Education in an interview on August 26, 2024 stated that “as Permanent Secretary I was the coordinator of the entire Ministry. It means that everything including policies and administration revolved around my office. Even though the politicians are trying to meddle into the role of the Permanent Secretary, but you cannot remove the fact that it is the statutory function of the office of the Permanent Secretary”.

Strategic Measures Set Up by the Civil Service in Achieving the Policy Objectives of the Rivers State Government from 2007-2023

Respondents from the different Ministries indicated that the administrative mechanisms of the respective Ministries provided the framework and operational guidelines by which the various policy objectives of the government under review were achieved. For instance, in the Ministry of Education, the Civil Service Reforms Act of 1988 provides that the Ministry has fourteen (14) structural Departments, with specific functions and administrative structure with the Honourable Commissioner as the Head and Chief Executive Officer, while the Permanent Secretary is the Chief Accounting Officer in the Ministry. The respective Directors and Heads of Departments form the Management Team of the Ministry. The Ministry’s Management Team consists of Directors and Heads of Departments as follows: Director of Administration; Director, Finance and Supply; Director Planning and Research; Director, Secondary Education; Director, Basic/Teacher Education; Director, Science and Technology; Director, Quality Assurance; Director, Examinations and Records; Director, Women and Special Education; Director, Higher Education. For effective performance of its statutory functions, the Parastatals and Boards operate under the ambit of the Ministry, which has oversight and supervisory functions over them. According to the Provisions of the Civil Service Reforms Decree 43 of 1988, all correspondences from the Boards and Parastatals to the Governor are required to be routed through the Ministry for proper supervision and accountability.

Respondents indicated the Ministry of Health also achieves its policy objectives through the administrative framework in line with the civil service operational mechanism. At the helm of affairs is the Honourable Commissioner who is the Chief Executive Officer and Head of the Ministry, while the Permanent Secretary is the Chief Accounting Officer of the Ministry. The Permanent Secretary has under his/her direct control Directors and Heads of various Departments as follows: Director, Administration; Director, Planning Research and Statistics; Director, Public Health Services; Director, Medical Services; Director, Finance and Accounts; Director, Pharmaceutical Services; Director, Nursing Services, as well

as Director, Special Services. In an oral interview with Director of Administration in the Ministry on Friday August 19, 2024, each Director in the Ministry is a professional and expert in his area of specialisation and brings in his wealth of experience to bear in the policy formulation and processes, as well as activities in the Ministry. They all work in synergy to achieve the overall objectives of the Ministry and also ensure that policies and programmes are implemented to the latter. The Directors, all put together, with the Permanent Secretary and Honourable Commissioner form the Management Team of the Ministry.

Figure 1. Organogram of Rivers State Ministry of Health
 Source: RSMoH Annual Report (2020)

From 2007-2015, the Ministry of Agriculture achieved its strategic measures through a policy implementation chart. Its broad agricultural policy is sub divided into Large Scale Agriculture and Small/Medium Scale Agriculture. Under the large scale agriculture, we have the following: Banana Project, Fish Farms, New Oil Palm project, Risonpalm, Delta Rubber, Agro- Industrial Villages, Songhai Farms, Cassava Project, Aqua Tourism, as well as other initiatives. On the other hand the small/medium scale agriculture policies are: the Agricultural Development Project (ADP), School-to-Land (STL), FADAMA III, IFAD CBRMP, as well as the Rivers State Sustainable Development Agency intervention. In an oral interview with Director of Rserach and Statistics in the Ministry of Agriculture in his office on Friday August 19, 2024, the strategic measures in achieving the policy objectives in the Ministry are in line with the administrative mechanism and civil service rules which provides for a clear cut hierarchical structure un the administrative process. At the helm of affairs is the Honourable Commissioner, who is the Chief Executive Officer in the Ministry, while the Permanent Secretary is the Chief Accounting Officer in the Ministry. A total of eight Directors are in charge of various Departments and sub divisions in the Ministry. They also form the Management Team in the Ministry.

In an interview with a retired Permanent Secretary of the Rivers State Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry achieved its roles through laid down principles and procedures. According to him, “the Chief Adviser to the Honourable Commissioner is the Permanent Secretary. The Chief Adviser to the Permanent Secretary are the Directors in the Ministry. A Commissioner is not supposed to by-pass the Permanent Secretary to the Directors, except for personal reasons. All official line of communication must follow the laid down procedures. The Management Team meets weekly to discuss issues within the mandates of the Ministry. At the meeting, every Director/Head of Department makes necessary input regarding the

activities of his/her Department. It is therefrom that policy decisions are reached and deduced to memoranda, which are sent to the Executive Council through the Commissioner. Such memoranda are passed through the Office of the Secretary to the State Government (Cabinet Office), which schedules them in the meeting. It, therefore, implies that such policies result from expertise, experience and feedback from the respective field officers in the Ministry”.

Figure 2. Illustrating Policy Implementation Chart of Rivers State Ministry of Agriculture
 Source: RSMoA, (2014)

Another retired Permanent Secretary from Ministry of Education averred that “the management of the Ministry is structured in the Department headed by a Director. The Director interfaces and relates with line officers who carry out relevant directives in the implementation of policies and programmes and in turn bring back feedbacks on the outcome of policies that would enable them advice government. The Directors and Permanent Secretary form the Management Team of the Ministry. Management meetings hold at least once in three months, however, there were also emergency or extra ordinary management meetings when the need arises”. He further stated that it was imperative to ensure that policies are monitored in order to get the desired result. According to him, “to succeed, you must create a group of trusted persons who would supervise supervisors. During my time I relied so much on statistics. So I had statistics of all the schools in Rivers State which enabled us plan in the Ministry. I made efforts to ensure that subordinates given various responsibilities were strictly supervised. To achieve this, I ensured that if I sent a group of people on supervision, I also sent another group unknown to the earlier group to supervise the supervisors. By this, I got the true picture of what was happening in the field, whether the supervisors were carrying out their assignments properly or not. If there is a memo on activities to be performed or actions to be carried out in the Ministry, I as the Permanent Secretary prepared the memo, even though it is the Honourable Commissioner that will sign it, before it is passed on to the Governor directly or to the Executive Council through the Office of the Secretary to the State Government. Also, when the Governor wants a policy to be introduced, he briefs the Honourable Commissioner, the Honourable Commissioner brings it down to the Ministry. He, in turn, briefs the Permanent Secretary. The Permanent Secretary will convene a Management meeting which will discuss the matter properly. If it is an issue that will be passed to a specialised Department, it will be referred to the Department and the Department will work on it and produce a report to that effect. Such report is brought back to the Management of the Ministry. It is deliberated upon and fine-tuned, with other Heads of Department making their inputs. That document will now be sent through the Honourable Commissioner with a

forwarding letter to the State Executive Council for deliberation and approval. If the State Executive Council approves it, it becomes a policy which the Ministry can formally comply with and implement”.

In the same vein, another retired Permanent Secretary in the Ministry of Health in an interview on August 31, 2024, alluded that the structure for the implementation of policies and programmes of government are stipulated in the civil service guidelines and rules. According to her, “the Permanent Secretary coordinates all the activities of the Ministry with the aid of Directors and Heads of the various Departments in the Ministry who form the Management Team of the Ministry. Each Director/Head of Department is a professional in his or her field that supervises the activities of the Department and is responsible to the Commissioner through the Permanent Secretary. If a policy comes from the government, it passes through the Commissioner down to the Permanent Secretary, who directs the relevant Department to make input. When such input is made, it is sent back to the Governor through the Commissioner and then presented at the Executive Council meeting. Once it is approved by the Executive Council, it then becomes an official government policy that is now brought back to the Ministry for implementation”. She further states that “the main function of the civil servant is the implementation of government policies and programmes and so we adopt measures to ensure effective implementation of such programmes. For me, I tried to ensure that duties were carried out to the letter and in order not to fail in the implementation of programmes due to sabotage of some staff, which of course is usually the case, I had to make a staff I identified could jeopardize or sabotage the implementation process, the Team Leader. This is to give him or her that responsibility so that he/she would be duty bound to deliver. However, I made the more serious and result-oriented staff keep a close watch on him or her and by so doing, we successfully implemented most of the programmes and policies in the Ministry during my time”.

Conclusion

The civil service is the main machinery by which government policies and programmes are implemented and as a result its importance cannot be over emphasised. The quality of governance and development in a State is seen from the quality of the implementation of policies and programmes by the civil service and so a healthy well intentioned and professional civil service is necessary to achieve the desired development for a society. The civil service operates under guidelines, principles and rules in order to achieve its object. It is the wheel on which the activities of government revolve. While the politicians make policies, the civil service is saddled with the implementation of such policies. No policy can take effect without implementation by the civil service, no matter how good and well intention such policy is. To this effect, a proper synergy between the civil service and policy makers cannot be over emphasized. An effective civil service is a variable tool for the overall development of the State.

The overall importance of the civil service in the implementation of government programmes and policies cannot be overemphasised. In this study, we observed that the Rivers State civil service, like every other civil service has the requisite structure and framework for effective service delivery. Over the years the civil servants have demonstrated willingness to perform their functional and constitutional responsibilities. There is an obvious reality that the civil servants played significant role in the policy objectives of the Rivers State Government from 2007 to 2021. We observed that there were significant differences in the roles played by civil servants in the different Ministries, as well as the two administrations. However, implementation of public programmes and policies remained constant by the two administrations. The Rivers State civil service has also evolved strategic measures in achieving the policy objectives of government. These are entrenched in the guidelines, procedures codes and rules governing the service. These guidelines are mechanical in nature and so are routinely applied in the operational mechanism of the civil service activities. Civil servants were used more between 2007 and 2015 than in 2015 and 2023. The resultant effect is the gap in the policy formulation measures between the two administrations. Both the politicians and the civil servant must realize that they both are partners in the quest to achieve the needed and desired development of the society. In order words, they two must work symbiotically to realize the goals and purpose of the state. This should be done by each playing by

the rules and principles for which it was set up. Several challenges were identified to hamper the proper functioning of the civil servants in the realization of their functions. Amongst such is conflict of interest between the politicians/political office holders and the civil servants, improper recruitment into the service, lack of training and re-training of civil servants as well as improper motivation of civil servants to carry out their duties. The civil service must be well equipped with the right personnel and professional administrators that have the capacity to interpret government rules and regulations as well as apply them for proper and effective implementation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this research:

1. The Rivers State Government should provide an enabling environment to help the civil service achieve its goal of a qualitative and efficient service delivery.
2. Given the important role played by the civil servants in policy formulation, Permanent Secretaries should be made to be members of the State Executive Council in order to improve the quality of debate and decision making of policies and programmes.
3. The Rivers State Government should establish an Administrative Training Institute, which would train and retrain the senior civil servants as well as elected politicians and political appointees on various techniques in governance as well as strategic techniques in policy formulation, implementation and evaluation.
4. To solve the problem of capacity in personnel, there should be training and re-training of civil servants in professional administration.
5. Recruitment into the Rivers State civil service should be made on merit, rather than through political patronage, religious, ethnic and social considerations.
6. Civil Servants at the Management level should be members of their professional organisations.
7. Government should ensure and enhance the funding capacity of the civil servants in order to carry out their job effectively and efficiently.

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